

Separation of Thallium(I), Mercury(II), Silver(I), and Copper(II) by Ion-exchange Chromatography

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Though thallium (III) has been separated from aluminium, gallium, and indium on Dowex-1 by Kraus *et al.*¹ using 4 *M* perchloric acid as eluent, no ion-exchange separation methods involving thallium (I) are available. Attempts have been made in this communication to study the elution characteristics of thallium(I) and utilise them for separating it from silver, mercury(II), and copper(II) in binary combination.

All elution studies for thallium (I) as nitrate (20 ml of 0.1 *N* solution) were performed on a 15.0 × 1.0 cm column of Amberlite IR—120 (AR) resin in sodium form (capacity ≈ 47 m.e.). The elutions were carried out at 3 ml/cm²/min. flow rate. Its elution was first tried with 5% nitric acid solution which eluted it not as thallium (I) but as thallium (III), making its estimation in the effluent with potassium iodate² unsatisfactory. Elutions were then tried with a 5% solution of sodium nitrate and 2% and 5% solutions of sodium nitrite. Sodium nitrate eluted it in a large number of fractions. Thallium started coming in this case from the very first fraction. Sodium nitrite (2%) could not elute it up to the first twenty fractions of 20ml each, though later it also eluted thallium in a large number of fractions. Sodium sulphate solutions of 2, 5, 7 and 10% were then used. These eluted thallium(I) satisfactorily (Fig. 1) and effluents in all cases could be estimated volumetrically by potassium iodate smoothly. These studies indicate the possibilities of separating thallium(I) from the ions that could be eluted conveniently with 2% sodium nitrite solutions, e.g. silver³, mercury (II)⁴, and copper⁵.

Separation of Thallium(I) from Mercury (II), Silver (I), and Copper (II) in Binary Mixtures.—All separations were performed with 10 ml each of their 0.1 *N* solutions in binary combinations. Total influent volume was thus 20 ml in each case. The mixed solutions (Hg—Tl, Ag—Tl, or Cu—Tl) were allowed to percolate through the sodium form of the resin column (15.0 × 1.0 cm Amberlite IR—120) at 3 ml/cm²/min. flow rate. The constituent ions were tested in the effluent by suitable spot tests. These were found to be absent in all combinations. After the sorption step, the column was washed with distilled water and elution started for the first component (mercury, silver, or copper) with 2% sodium nitrite. The 20-ml fractions of the eluate were collected and titrated with suitable titres³⁻⁵ for estimating the ion concerned, after destroying the nitrite ion in it in the usual way. After complete elution of the first component, the eluent was changed. Thallium(I) was then eluted with 10% sodium sulphate solution. All 20-ml fractions for it were collected and titrated with potassium iodate² in presence of HCl (conc.). Thallium (1 m.e. in 1:1 mixtures,

1. *J. Phys. Chem.* 1954, 58, 11.
2. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co. 1956, p. 366.
3. Bhatnagar and Shukla, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 32, 777.
4. Bhatnagar and Pendse, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 226.
5. Bhatnagar *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1963, 1, 159.

total influent volume 20 ml) was eluted completely in eleven or twelve fractions in all cases. All separations for the pairs Hg—Tl, Ag—Tl, and Cu—Tl (all 1:1 mixtures) were quantitative (Fig. 2).

Effluent vol. (ml),
FIG. 1

Effluent vol. (ml).
FIG. 2

Successful separations were performed with differing mixture compositions between 9:1 and 1:9 of mercury (π), silver, or copper in binary combinations with thallium (ι).